

FEATURES OF THE FUNCTIONING OF MINING TERMINOLOGY IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The article deals with the features of the functioning of the terms of mining terminology in English. At the heart of the article of semantic processes in the English language of mining terminology, three directions can be distinguished: reduction of meaning components; increase in components and substitution.

Keywords: mining terminology, feature, English language, component, process

In modern linguistics, the mechanism for the formation of new meanings is described as follows: words are not just signs, determined not only by the formal correspondence of a given content and a given sound expression. Words are complex units, and the meaning of a word depends on many factors, for example, the use of a word in speech, in specialized literature, as well as such extra linguistic factors as the social life of a people, the conditions for its existence and development. In connection with the development of social progress, science and technology, culture, as well as Interlingua communication, new concepts arise in each language. To reflect them in the lexicon, there are the following possibilities:

1. creation of a new word;
2. expansion of the semantic structure of the word already in the language;
3. differentiation of meanings between existing words.

The concept that underlies the lexical meaning of the term is characterized by blurred boundaries. Due to this “fuzziness”, the lexical meaning of a word can

increase in volume, cover several designations of objects, for example: *face - yuz, tubi, terish*.

It has been established that for the English mountain terminology system, as for any other, a characteristic feature is proximity to the commonly used vocabulary. This feature is closely related to the functional variability of the term, which moves in two directions: differentiation and integration; is displayed in the pragmatic mobility of terminological units that migrate from common vocabulary to special terminology and vice versa.

The process of transition of a commonly used word into the category of terms can be traced on the example of the term *reeler – to reel - aylanmoq*, in mining terminology this term will have the meaning - *o'rash mashinasi*.

At the heart of the semantic processes of English mining terminology, three directions can be distinguished: reduction of meaning components; increase in components and substitution (replacement of some components for others). On the way to reduce the components of the denotative meaning, you can see the process of its expansion, and on the way to increase the components, respectively, the process of narrowing.

For example: to doctor in mining is described as to dress the maggy heads (past navli rudani qayta ishlash), coming from ore-dressing treatment (rudani boyitish jarayoni).

Also, the borrowing of words from other term systems or common vocabulary plays an important role in understanding the concept of a term. In most cases, borrowings follow the principle of adjacency of the designated concepts, for example: *gallery - galereya, konchilikda - er osti galereyasi, ya'ni material yig'ish uchun tunnel*.

Thus, it can be traced that the formation of a word as a term takes place in several stages: the creation of a term, for example, by borrowing from another terminological system or from common vocabulary, the expansion or narrowing of

its semantics in connection with the rapidly developing progress in the field of mining.

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